

LEVERAGING COMPUTER INTEGRATED MANUFACTURING FOR MARKET RESILIENCE AND SUSTAINABLE GROWTH OF SMES: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY OF BRITISH SMES

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Abstract

For a long time, the fundamental cause of regulating the operations of SMEs at lower efficiency was a lack of marketing forces, the use of information systems, modularity, and cost-effective manufacturing solutions. In view of the importance of the aforementioned factors, a model was considered for the Computer Integrated Manufacturing (CIM) implementation in SMEs. An empirical study in British SMEs was carried out to test the established model to facilitate CIM adoption. Findings revealed that majority of SMEs reported influence of CIM implementation in various marketing factors i.e. new markets for new products–53%, building market share with existing and new products–92%, defending market share–76%, competitiveness–62%, stability–59%, profitability–59%, and marketing–76% to a very great, certain and some extent. Moreover, information systems supported SMEs in managing information–84%. Additionally, information systems supported SMEs in cost control, capacity and production planning, scheduling, and material control–58% to a very great, certain, and to some extent. Findings of modularity factors revealed that CIM has influenced the production variety–84%, reduced delivery time–84%, managing complexity–92%, flexibility in product design–88%, quick transformation–50%, cost reduction of manufacturing–92%, product performance–84%, support after sales–88%, delivery dates–96%, shorter lead time to deliver–88%, consistent quality–100%, and rapid change in product design–88% to a very great, certain and to some extent collectively. In cost-effective solutions, CIM has contributed to responsive planning and control–88%, reliable process–100%, workforce flexibility–96%, and reliable supply chains–96% to a very great, certain, and to some extent collectively. Findings divulge that CIM implementation plays a dynamic role in the sustainable growth of SMEs.

1. Introduction

For a long time, the fundamental cause of regulating the operations of SMEs at lower efficiency was a lack of marketing forces, use of information systems, modularity and cost-effective manufacturing solutions. Owing to the substantial impact SMEs have on the global economy, strategies for the sustainable growth of SMEs have gained momentum [1]. In fact, Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) are the backbone of the economy of every country [2]. SMEs' worth cannot be underestimated because of their contribution to the gross domestic product (GDP), generation of new job opportunities [3] and aid in export [4], but globalization has created a challenging environment for SMEs to sustain in the market. It is because globalization increases the complexity of the decision process due to long lead time, which results in transportation costs [5]. The long-term goal for all SMEs, especially manufacturing SMEs, is to stay and grow in business and earn profit [6]. The business environment of ongoing century can be characterised by globalisation with a variety of products and varying demands [5]. Understanding the changing business environment is essential for manufacturing SMEs. Globalisation has deeply changed the attitude of customers. Nowadays, customers want high-quality products at minimum cost [7], and shorter lead times with customised requirements [8]. The success of organisations depends upon the factors that play a predominant role in market share and profitability, such as performance of delivery, customisation, and waste reduction. CIM (Computer Integrated Manufacturing) is the most emerging strategy that unfolds the opportunity to overcome the manufacturing cost and delays in the transfer of information.

Computer Integrated Manufacturing (CIM) is the structure through which different functions such as engineering, manufacturing and marketing are being integrated with the help of information technologies [9]. In a wide approach, CIM comprises the integration of the total setup of the business, i.e., vendor to consume [10]. It controls the manufacturing process from the conception of the product to the end user [11]. Throughout business integration, CIM may be used as a strategy for resource planning of enterprises. This points out the connection between CIM and business process re-engineering with an aim to attain integration in order to improve productivity and quality [12]. The

motivation for SMEs towards CIM is based on the need to rapidly respond to the changes as compared to the past. Enterprises adopt new technologies related to CIM to remain competitive and productive [13]. CIM assures many benefits i.e., reduced work-in-progress (WIP) inventory, better machine utilisation, improved productivity of working capital, cheap labour costs, less of machine tools, cut in lead times, the best utilisation of floor space, shrunk set-up costs and consistency in product quality [7]. In today's business environment, in fact, firms must be able to innovate rapidly [11]. Implementing CIM creates more growth opportunities for SMEs to produce new products and grasp new markets, in contrast to SMEs putting their faith in old-fashioned manufacturing technologies and common tactics. Moreover, the implementation of CIM systems can be an opportunity to transition to smart manufacturing. For that, [14] have provided the framework for intelligent CIM in IoT setting. Towards this, [15] have also discussed the evolution of CIM to smart manufacturing systems. SMEs practicing CIM in fact, create a chain of choices for near-future entrance into new markets and businesses as well. Rising market diversity complicates both process planning and product development since segment and niche solidity are shrinking gradually as time passes. Nowadays, clients have more awareness about the alternative options, and their increasing awareness makes it challenging to engage in usual differentiation approaches based on both quality and image. In such plentiful alternatives available, customers can demand different options, renewed ideas, the best functionality and multiple connections with vendors that make niches inside niches [16]. The areas of information in which SMEs frequently need support are: (a) export market start-up guidance and support, (b) market info, especially on broad markets, (c) education of technological management and (d) facts and figures related to overall economic situations which may affect upcoming market growth and necessities.

This is the era of information technology, which leads SMEs towards competitive advantage (Asil & Naralan, 2016). In order to overcome the challenges of enterprise information integration and its promotion, various manufacturing systems are being used, and CIM is one of them [17]. Entrance to international markets is made easy by globalisation [18], and reduced communication distance with

rapid access to information in a minimum time. Rapid and continuous advancement in computer-based technologies enhanced the competitiveness of enterprises [19]. Latest developments in the move of information have seen a rise in the usage of advanced manufacturing technologies for the adoption of smart manufacturing, which has some benefits to the SMEs in overall improvement of a production system in terms of human and machine decision-making capability enhancement [20].

This research paper is an extended version of the conference paper presented by Marri H.B. et al. [21]. It carried out an empirical investigation in British SMEs to determine the role of information systems, modularity, marketing, and cheaper solutions for CIM implementation in SMEs.

1.2. Impact of cheaper solution, marketing, modularity, and information system, on the CIM implementation in SMEs

Globalisation, together with technological change, has altered the approaches to environment of doing business in every industry. SMEs need additional caution in the investments [22]. As [23] stated that in reality, SMEs face a conflict situation that the future of SMEs demands balanced investment decisions for the acquisition of advanced technologies and new methods. As observed by [24], during the last decade, manufacturing has been in a drastic and changing environment. Holt [25] proposed to develop a strategy later as a problem definition. Furthermore, [26] proposed a model of manufacturing strategy that bonds objectives of the business, its marketing strategy, manufacturing process, order-winning criteria and manufacturing infrastructure together.

A study carried out by [27] engaged small manufacturing firms and witnessed that innovative enterprises are making better decisions for the adoption of new technology as compared to non-innovative enterprises. Additionally, [28] carried out a survey of two hundred twenty-two manufacturing firms that have adopted advanced manufacturing technologies (AMTs) and concluded that there had a moderately significant effect which quality of planning system play between the strategic change and the success of effective implementation. Besides this, [29] stated that both changes in job and extensive business processes would be essential in order to attain the estimated outcomes from new

technology, for each departmental function and position of the organisation. These types of routine work changes would involve important change management, as the customer service strategy and use of new technology link would be ensured. Moreover, [30] quoted that the main features for the successful integration between manufacturing flexibility and business strategy are a choice of well-adjusted projects' portfolio and adequate advancement of intellectual assets as well, because both are closely linked with the speedy changing markets closely [31].

For small firms [32], has identified five major difficulties which include: (i) business size, (ii) Cash flow, (iii) tactical nature customer-related problems, (iv) dearth of marketing proficiency and (v) business size. As stated by [33], CIM involves the integration of overall managerial functions, for example: personnel, design, engineering, marketing, finance and accounting. In connection with that [34] has recommended to marketing manufacturing a support tool that would act as an integrated to this link. Likewise, [35] has provided a review on the innovation strategies and also presented a detailed overview of the specified field. In addition, [36] laid much emphasis on the influence of the architecture of market requirements and their impact on the necessities related to the investment in education of the market. Moreover, [37] investigated the link between market strategies and technology broadly. There are several other studies [38], [39], [40], [41] that have observed the importance of the interface between manufacturing and marketing in purchasing, design and production planning functions.

Purchasing automatically is one of the integral characteristics of CIM adoption for SMEs. Most of the operations need the purchase of a varied range of materials and services, and usually their quantity and cost are increasing due to the considerations of organizations towards their core activities. Purchasing should be done earlier in the product development phase, with the involvement of design and planning departments, and contracts, if not, quotations have been made with reliable suppliers. There might be established alternatives with proposed settings on delivery time, quantity and price. This whole related information might be kept on the database of vendor in order to capable to monitor and analyse the results in relation to the

accomplished and set against the quality level and delivery time. Purchased orders resulting from MRP are to be fulfil planned orders, if unavailability of such a database. As [42] stated that the characteristic of the ideal supplier depends upon the effective organization of the company's own suppliers. EDI not only provides an opportunity to the companies for reducing suppliers, but due to the advantage of quick communication, also increases their purchasing speed. EDI provides a path to communicate the organizations' purchasing, shipping and billing from one enterprise to another. It also streamlines the firms' operations and overcomes the delivery delays that result from the huge documentation [43].

Management of information is a major right of way for successful manufacturing systems. Moreover, the deployment of proper information systems practices improves the performance of Enterprises [44]. The industrial enterprise is an integration of complicated organizational and technical systems that operate different control and automated systems. Depending on the scope of automation of the enterprise, different classes of information systems and technologies are used to solve different management tasks. However, information systems directly support production, design, and technological activity of the enterprise in the manufacturing [45]. Hence, [46] have developed a database system, with the help of this system, complex data not only can be manipulated, but complex relationships can also be maintained between the data because of its advanced integrity mechanism and has the ability to take corrective actions in certain circumstances. In recent trends of spreading information usage of teleconferencing, videos, CD-ROMs, and multimedia packages have increased. There are various benefits of information management database i.e., increased information delivery speed, better understanding of complex information, higher information preservation and lateral thinking stimulation. In addition, efficient management of the data and information flows serves as a major source for decision-making in the field of automation of the enterprise [45]. Similarly, [47] have defined the launching of a technology bank through the World Wide Web (WWW) as an experimental means for technology transfer whose aims were only to focus on studying issues in university research through the medium of the

Internet. They, in their paper, have offered the technology bank to industrialists. The navigation paths offer suitable forms and understanding of the information for communication between industry and academia.

There are very low numbers of SMEs that adopt CIM in their operations. However, large organisations report CIM as one of the highly ranked strategies [48]. Marketing in small firms is not well structured, planned or seen as formal as compared to large organisations [49]. Globalisation, advances in information and competitiveness put the focus of SMEs towards customer relationships [50]. This is very critical for SMEs in the current global competitive circumstances of consumer-oriented marketing, which force SMEs to strengthen themselves with integrated information systems. Automation has made capable SMEs to take advantage of improved customer service [51]. Primarily CIM system incorporates two areas of operations mentioned by [52] i.e., capability of human and logistics planning. Major hitches in the development and adoption of CIM information systems contain: Automation Island, system segregation and lack of ability to move towards upcoming technology, as stated by [53].

Modularity is an approach practiced gaining different manufacturing with cut-down costs. This procedure attempts to produce manufacturing output in interchangeable subassemblies or modules. In such a sense, they therefore offered purchasers their required option. In case a customer can specify different aspects, i.e., colour, engine size, tires etc., for the purchase of a new car. Modules of different aspects, i.e., a variety of engine sizes, varying coloured bodies, fashion rims and tires, can produce this type of variety product and assemble different modules of customer choice for the final product, rather than producing different models of the same product. CIM is a helpful technology for SMEs to ensure the product or services of such different variety to satisfy customer needs, market requirements and a helpful tool to support and ensure the designs for the latest goods and services which fulfil the market demands.

The impact of information systems, marketing, modularity, and cheaper ways and means on the adaptation of Computer Integrated Manufacturing in SMEs has been evaluated with the help of an empirical investigation carried out in British SMEs.

2. **An empirical study with British SMEs**
 We carried out an empirical study in the British SMEs having a workforce not over than 500 with the

help of a questionnaire. Seven-point Likert scale was used for the collection of data.

Figure 1: Model to illustrate the impact of marketing, information systems, modularity, and low-cost solutions on the CIM implementation.

Parameters mentioned in Fig. 1 are explained from the CIM implementation in the SMEs' point of view. Detail is given in succeeding sections. It is worth mentioning that this paper is the updated version of the paper presented by the lead and corresponding author Marri H.B in an international conference in USA. This version holds detailed results and discussion.

3. **Results**

This section presents the outcomes of the empirical investigation of the framework established for the implementation of CIM. It encompasses four sub-sections i.e., marketing objectives of SMEs, role of information system in CIM implementation, modularity and low-cost solutions.

3.1 SMEs Marketing objectives

In this research study, SMEs were enquired about the achievements concerning the marketing objectives after implementing CIM. SMEs were also asked to provide information on the improvement

or increase in the various factors on a seven-point Likert scale, 1-7, ranging from a very little to a very great improvement or increase. Findings for improving marketing parameters through the implementation of CIM are presented in Fig 2.

Figure 2: Improvement in marketing factors of SMEs through CIM implementation

Outcomes of the study revealed that 29 percent of SMEs ranked at the scale 7, which meant a very great improvement to defend market share or form market share and stay in business. 31% of SMEs have ranked at the scale 5 to defend market share or form market share and stay in business to some extent. Moreover, 16% of SMEs improved to some extent in defending market share, whereas 8% have rated a little improvement in staying in the business or defending market share. For building market share with existing and new products, a greater percentage of SMEs i.e., 53% have rated that they have improved to a certain extent in this objective. Moreover, like the percentage reported for the defending market share i.e., 31% SMEs scored that they have improved to some extent in building market share with new and existing products. Whereas 8% have reported improvement in building the market share with current and new products to a very great extent, and 8% have reported improvement to a little extent. For the objective of creating new markets for new products, 32% and 31% have reported improvement to a certain extent and slight improvement, respectively. Moreover, 8%

have reported some improvement, and 8% have reported a little improvement.

Besides, according to the findings of this research study, 25% of SMEs reported progress regarding their stabilized marketing and profitability growing after CIM implementation, as shown in Fig. 2. Also, another 25% SMEs reported that they made progress in all the above-mentioned market size areas. Likewise, 22% SMEs mentioned enough growth in all the parameters of market size among moderate competitors. 12% SMEs reported that they have made average growth with uncertain demand in the market with moderate competitors. Whereas 4% SMEs reported little product life cycle with moderate growth among lower competitors after CIM implementation.

Notwithstanding, half a percentage of SMEs reported progress to a certain extent regarding their stabilized marketing. In addition, 26% and 23% reported improvement to some extent and some improvement, respectively related to the stabilized markets. As shown in the Fig 2, the majority of the SMEs reported an increase in the stabilization of the market. For the market demand, one fourth of SMEs reported that they have made improvement the

market demand of the products. In addition, 22 percent reported improvement to some extent, whereas more than half of SMEs reported improvement to some extent, slight and a little improvement in the market demand.

Generally, SMEs have experienced notable growth in total areas of their market by the implementation of CIM. However, cumulatively, a high percentage of SMEs have reported an improvement in achieving the objectives of marketing after implementing the CIM, particularly in defending and building market share. However, SMEs have reported a slightly less improvement in creating new markets. This reflects that CIM helps SMEs in sustaining and building market shares. SMEs realised improvements in marketing objectives to a certain extent, who have implemented CIM. First, SMEs must detect the market range and products that are likely to be reached and produced, respectively. For matching the products with technologies of the modern era management of companies take appropriate measures so that the implementation of CIM systems cannot only attain operational benefits (better quality, improved performance and undersized lead time) but also strategic and marketing benefits as well. Furthermore, advantages like rapid response to alterations in the marketplace, more market share, the capability to produce customised products, reduced prices, quick product innovation increased companies' name and fame have all been attributed to the functionality of flexible Computer Integrated Manufacturing systems.

Implementing CIM has a significant effect on either keeping or increasing the share of the market and bringing new offerings to existing markets. Other researchers also agree with this, who have said that enterprises are investing a worthwhile amount in Advanced Manufacturing Systems in order to keep up with rapidly changing offerings in the market [52]. Obviously, in the sense of these findings core objective for the SMEs is to retain market shares by investing a handsome amount and efforts in order to keep pace with the rapidly changing products.

3.2 Information systems

The result of this empirical study shows that 84 %, 79%, 25% and 16% of SMEs reported that they have

implemented MRP, CAD/CAM, JIT and CAE information systems, respectively. In addition to that, only 4% of SMEs quoted that they have implemented PCI, EDI, CAPP and VPD information systems.

SMEs were also asked to provide information on the adequate support of information systems provided to their various operations on a seven-point Likert scale, 1-7, ranging from very poor to excellent, as shown in Fig. 3.

Results of this empirical study revealed that 34 percent of SMEs were of the view that information systems provided very good support in managing quality, 8% marked good support, 16% realized a moderate support, 34% reported fair support, whereas only 8% stated poor support that information systems provided in managing quality control. In addition, 8 percent of SMEs reported excellent support of information systems in material control, 34% described very good support, 16% stated good support, 8% marked moderate support, and 34% realized fair support of information systems for material control. Moreover, 8 percent of respondent SMEs reported excellent support of information systems in shopfloor control, 34% SMEs stated good support, and the same percentage (34%) realized moderate support, 16% marked fair support, whereas 8% reported poor support of information systems in controlling shopfloor operations. Likewise, 8 percent of SMEs marked the excellent support of information systems in scheduling the activities. 34%, 16% and 8% reported very good support, good support and fair support, respectively, and 34% realized fair support of the information system in scheduling the activities. Also, 8 percent of SMEs appreciated the role of information systems in production planning to an excellent level. 16%, 34% and 8% valued the very good, good and moderate support of information systems in the production planning, respectively, notwithstanding, 34% recognized the fair support of information systems in the production planning. Interestingly, the highest percentage from all the factors, however, like managing information, 16 percent of SMEs realized a very excellent support of information systems in capacity planning. Like the percentage of SMEs -34%- reported very good support of information systems in capacity planning and managing information as well.

Figure 3: Adequate support given to SMEs by information systems

Moreover, 8%, 34% and 8% SMEs received good, moderate and fair support from information systems in capacity planning, respectively. Whereas 34%, 8%, and 8% acknowledged good, moderate and fair support of information systems in managing the information, respectively. 8% SMEs scored the excellent support of information systems in sales and market, and same extent of support for controlling the cost, acknowledged the same percentage of SMEs i.e., 8%. However, 34% acknowledged very good support of information systems in sales and marketing and like percentage (34%) acknowledged good support of information systems in controlling the cost. Moreover, 34% SMEs realized moderate and fair support of information systems in controlling costs and sales and marketing, respectively. Only 8% SMEs acknowledged the fair support of information systems in controlling the cost. However, 16% SMEs reported poor support from information systems to sales and market factors.

Precisely, after CIM implementation, the information systems have provided the highest support to capacity planning and managing information, whereas: delivered a good level of support in the control of material, scheduling, & sales and marketing. Additionally, SMEs have

indicated an average level of support achieved through information systems in production planning, controlling of quality, cost and shopfloor operations. Aside, a few SMEs reported the poor support of information systems in sales and marketing, and a few SMEs conveyed poor support of information systems in controlling shopfloor operations and controlling the quality too. Generally, SMEs have attained good support from all information systems who have implemented CIM.

3.3 Modularity of the SMEs

Factors for the Modularity of the SMEs include persistent quality of product, rapid change in the design of product, short lead time, enhanced product performance, support after sales, dependable delivery dates, minimization in manufacturing cost, flexibility in product design, quick transformation, reduction in the development time, reduction in managerial complexity in product development and to increase in product variety as shown in Fig 4. SMEs were asked to provide information on the improvement or increase in the various factors of modularity on a seven-point Likert scale, 1-7, ranging from a very little to a very great improvement or increase.

Figure 4: Improvement in the Modulatory factors of SMEs

During this empirical study, 50% of SMEs quoted improvements to rapid change in the product design to a certain extent, 38% reported improvement in the rapid change in product design to some extent, 4% and 8% mentioned a slight improvement and little improvement in the rapid change in the product design, respectively, as shown in Fig 4. In addition, half of the percentage rated the highest category, and half rated the second highest category of the scale for the persistent quality. It means they agreed upon the improvement in maintaining the steady quality of products to a very great extent and to a certain extent. Cumulatively respondents rated it to a significant level, as shown in Fig 4. Moreover, half of the SMEs reported shortening the lead time to delivery to a very great extent and 38% quoted to a certain extent. In addition, eight percent and four percent reported a decrease in the lead time to some and slight extent. 88% of respondent SMEs rated improvement in the dependable delivery dates to a very great extent, in addition, 8 and 4 percent scored improvement to some extent and slight improvement respectively.

Moreover, 50% of the SMEs reported improvement in the after-sales support to a very great extent. 38% reported improvement in the after-sales support to a certain extent. 4% reported the improvement to some extent, whereas 8% reported the improvement in after-sales support to a slight extent. For improvement in the product performance, 42% of SMEs quantified an increase in the product performance to a very great extent and a similar percentage of SMEs reported an increase in the product performance to a certain extent. Only 16% reported some increase in the product performance. Interestingly, 92% of SMEs reported a reduction in the cost of manufacturing to a certain extent after CIM implementation, and 8% reported some reduction in the manufacturing cost. Next, 42%, 8%, 38%, and 12% SMEs reported improvement in the quick transformation to adopt changes to a very great extent, some extent, some improvement, and slight improvement, respectively. Further, for flexibility in product design, 38% reported that CIM implementation has assisted up to a certain extent. 50% of SMEs reported flexibility

in the product design to some extent. Notwithstanding 4% and 8% reported flexibility in the product design due to CIM up to slight and little improvement, respectively. Additionally, 54% of SMEs reported a reduction in managing the complexity to a certain extent, 38% reported improvement in managing the complexity to some extent, and 8% reported slight improvement in managing the complexity. 42% SMEs reported the benefit of CIM implementation in reducing the delivery time to a very great extent, a similar percentage reported a reduction in the delivery time to some extent, and 8% reported some reduction in the delivery time. Lastly, 42% of respondent SMEs reported improvement in product variety to a certain extent, and the same percentage reported improvement to some extent. In addition, 8%, and 8% of the respondent SMEs reported some improvement and a slight improvement in the product variety, respectively.

Briefly, SMEs quoted short delivery lead time, steady quality, timely delivery, support after sales, decrease development time and quick transmission (changeovers) as the most significant elements for the success due to the CIM implementation at the SMEs. In addition, rapid change in product design, flexible product design, reduction in the cost of manufacturing and managerial tasks' complexity, component standardisation, formation of product variety, all above factors act significantly for the success of CIM implementation. In addition to other criteria, this (modularity) also enabled SMEs to compete in the national and international markets. Interestingly, SMEs, for their success, have mentioned less important factors which include rapid change in product design, dependable delivery date, flexibility in the design of product and quick transformation (changeovers) than the rest of the factors. This is only because they have already attained success in those domains.

Persistent quality level is considered the most important of all manufacturing parameters, which illustrates the interest of manufacturing SMEs towards the quality improvement of what they produce. Some other important parameters found among all manufacturing parameters were reduction in the cost of manufacturing, short lead time to

deliver and rapid change in product design. CIM technologies were introduced to the manufacturing environment with an aim of increasing the ability of SMEs to improve design and manufacture or produce new products, enhance the performance of products, shorten lead time to deliver the products and also reduce the cost of manufacturing them. Therefore, the results of this empirical study explicit that the success of CIM implementation in SMEs is influenced by the modularity.

3.4 Cheaper solution

Five factors were used to determine the cheaper solution for small and medium enterprises (SMEs). Factors include reliable supply chain and processes, control system and responsive planning, workforce flexibility and excess capacity as shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5 presents the factors and their percentage of importance for cost-effective solutions. The outcomes of this empirical study confirm that 46 percent of SMEs realize that responsive planning and control systems as of a very great importance, 38% marked it as an important factor to a certain extent, 4% reported it as important to some extent and 12% considered it of some importance for a low-cost solution for SMEs who have implemented the CIM. Additionally, 46 percent of SMEs understood that reliable processes as of a very great importance, and 54% considered reliable processes as one of the important factors to a certain extent for inexpensive solution for SMEs who have implemented the CIM. Further, 30 percent of SMEs reflected workforce flexibility as one of the significant factors to a very great extent, 54% reported it as an important factor to a certain extent, 12% marked it important to some extent, whereas 4% realized it as of a very little importance. Moreover, 38 percent of SMEs stated reliable supply chains as of very great importance, 58% reported it as important to a certain extent, and 4% considered it as of little importance for working as one of the factors for affordable, low-cost solution to SMEs. For the role of excess capacity in assisting SMEs for a cheaper solution, 30 percent of SMEs reported it as of important to some extent, 30% highlighted it of some importance, 28% marked it of little importance, whereas 4% considered it of very little significance.

Figure 5: Low-cost solutions of the companies

Succinctly, the findings confirm that SMEs realize a reliable supply chain as the main principle for cheaper solutions for SMEs who have implemented the CIM. Same SMEs witnessed that quick planning and control systems respond, flexibility in workforce and reliable processes, all are also key criteria for a cheaper (low cost) solution. Whereas excess capacity is perceived as less important by these SMEs for their competitiveness in both national and international markets. Besides, SMEs realize all the areas, talked about in former lines, as central criteria, whereas excess capacity has been reported as an averagely important criterion for cheaper solutions implementations. SMEs have also seen excess capacity as having less importance, like the above-mentioned SMEs, for the cheaper solutions. Whereas: only a few SMEs of this empirical study have reported more importance for control systems and responsive planning and reliable processes as compared to other factors like excess capacity, workforce flexibility, as well as reliable supply chain, which are realized as not as important a criterion as a cheaper solution for global market competitiveness of SMEs. It is therefore clear from the outcomes of the empirical study that the success of CIM implementation in SMEs relies on the cheaper solutions in order to achieve global market competitiveness.

4. Conclusion and recommendations

In this research paper, concerned literature for the SMEs' experience of CIM implementation has been

reviewed, related to the information system, marketing, modularity and cheaper solutions. A conceptual model was framed and tested through evidence from an empirical study carried out within British SMEs.

In marketing factors, nearly to quarter of the SMEs reported that CIM assisted them in sustaining the competition and creating new markets for new products to a very great extent. Less than a quarter of SMEs realized the influence of CIM to improve with respect to competitors and build market share with existing and new products. Whereas less than a quarter percentage of SMEs either slight or a little improvement was noticed in creating new markets for new products, building market share with existing or new products, increasing market demand and profitability. Moreover, the majority of SMEs could notice a little increase in profitability. An average improvement or influence of CIM was reported in the marketing factors. In order to cope with such a challenge, marketing methods i.e., market segmentation, market segregation, and product differentiation, essentially be followed by SMEs, which will typically help SMEs in capitalizing markets.

Information systems strongly supported in managing the information, yet provided good support to capacity planning, production planning, scheduling and material control. Nevertheless, information systems averagely supported cost control, sales, shopfloor control, quality control and sales and market. Interestingly, a few SMEs also reported poor

support of information systems in sales and market, shop floor operations control, and in controlling quality. It is because there a very less SMEs' information systems. In order to get the most support for the information systems, it is essential for SMEs to strengthen working relationships with both customers and suppliers during the implementation of CIM in SMEs. This relationship can assist SMEs not only to get information for materials, equipment and components but also information concerning the technological updating of their operations. Moreover, this is very critical for SMEs in the current global competitive circumstances of consumer-oriented marketing, which force SMEs to strengthen themselves with integrated information systems. Currently, manufacturing organizations are switching to smart manufacturing for higher productivity and performance. CIM related technologies will definitely help SMEs with the advancement and implementation of smart manufacturing.

In modularity, SMEs have significantly improved in meeting delivery dates with improvement in shorter lead times to deliver by providing consistent quality and support after sales. Moreover, a good improvement was also realized in improved product performance, reduced development time and manufacturing cost reduction. An average improvement was also reported in reducing managing complexity, rapid change in product design, and flexibility in product design. Yet, a few SMEs also reported a little improvement in the flexibility and rapid change in product design. In order to do that, it is essential for firms to ensure the compatibility of the CIM system with their strategic directions to ensure the achievement of goals and objectives.

Moreover, SMEs realized that reliable processes, responsive planning and control systems, reliable supply chains, and workforce flexibility were the important, least cost solution factors for the success of CIM implementation in SMEs. Excess in capacity was reported as an average least cost solution factor for supporting the CIM implementation. Yet, a few SMEs' workforce flexibility and excess capacity are considered of a very little importance for the implementation of CIM. Large enterprises usually start and introduce the computer-aided technologies with their pilot application in one of the operating companies or in their department. In such a way,

large enterprises use pilot implementation for learning and experiencing the lessons in order to decrease the chances of failures in subsequent applications. In contrast to large enterprises, most SMEs cannot adopt such a pilot application because of their small size and lack of economic resources, but with the use of cheaper solutions and modularity, which will be more feasible approaches to adopt this research.

Additionally, SMEs have to improve their productivity for their survival in the global market. Increase in productivity not only satisfies their customers' demands but also helps them to compete in the market nationally and internationally. It is also to be expected that its (CIM) adoption leads the way to resolve the dilemma of eliminating some of the choices that negatively affect the productivity. Some specific mechanisms in this connection are (i) a sharp reduction in both work in progress (WIP) and goods inventories, (ii) a sharp increase in output per machine, because of improved speed of operations and rate of utilisation.

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